

CREATIVITY OF SECONDARY SCIENCE STUDENTS THROUGH INSTRUCTIONAL COMIC STRIPS APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

In an effort to examine alternative strategies that enhance creative outcomes in science education, this study investigated the effectiveness of comic strip approach in the classroom setting. This study assessed the creativity of students using comic strip instruction in science, as comic strips have been found to enhance student creativity. A quasi-experimental research design was employed. Adapted creativity rubrics were administered to Grade 8 students of Tongantongan National High School. Two intact sections were selected, with one group of 47 students exposed to a comic strip approach and the other group of 42 students taught using conventional methods. The findings revealed that students in the comic strip group showed a notable increase in creativity scores, achieving a score of 7.42 (very high level of creativity) after the intervention from 5.84 (high level of creativity). The analysis of covariance also showed that their creativity was significantly different compared to those taught conventionally, with an overall creativity p-value of 0.000 and an F-value of 3003.51. The results confirmed that comic strip instruction significantly enhances student creativity, particularly in indicators such as fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. However, the connection indicator showed no significant difference, suggesting the need for targeted activities to reinforce this skill. Based on the findings, it is recommended that science educators adopt comic strip instruction to foster creative thinking. Additionally, lesson designs should include activities that support students in linking and synthesizing ideas. Future researchers may explore strategies to strengthen students' ability to form meaningful connections in creative tasks.

Keywords: *Comic Strips Approach, Comic Strips, Creativity, Students' Creativity.*

INTRODUCTION

Educational methodologies often add creative media nowadays to encourage students to participate more and perform better. In many parts of the world, comic strips are well regarded for helping students understand difficult things more clearly. Research has demonstrated their effectiveness in enhancing motivation across various educational settings. While there are many tool educators can use to enhance creativity of students, The Philippines' rank in international assessments like PISA remains low.

The Philippines has consistently struggled in international assessments, and despite several attempts at educational reform, the country continues to fall short of global standards. The results from the 2023 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) revealed that Filipino students scored an average of 14 out of 60 in creative thinking, which is newly added in the assessment, far below the OECD average of 33. Only 22% of students reached the baseline level, and just 6% were top performers, which is under the 27% OECD average (OECD, 2023). These results emphasize a serious gap in learners' ability to generate, express, and evaluate original ideas. This is also evident among the students of Tongantongan National High School since many students cannot express ideas or make own connections through explaining science topics to real life applications or settings with their creative thinking. With creativity being essential in today's problem-solving and learning environments, there is a pressing need to explore strategies. The researcher recognizes this problem and addressed the issue in understanding science concepts through an innovative solution through Comic strips.

Comic strips have shown promise in developing creativity among students, a critical skill for problem-solving and innovation. Likewise, they have been found to increase student engagement and creativity while learning science concepts like the digestive system, reinforcing their effectiveness as teaching tools (Calejesan & Buniel, 2021). Moreover, visual and narrative aids have proven to foster creativity and higher-order thinking, making them an invaluable resource in education (Enteria & Casumpang, 2019).

This research is important because it addresses the issue of creativity in science education. Using comic strips as part of teaching strategies helps better understand ideas and develops a creative environment for critical thinking and problem-solving. The results of this study can be utilized as a model by other schools in the Philippines to help formulate plans, which will lead toward national educational advancement.

Research Objectives

This study assessed the students' creativity through the use of Comic Strips in the teaching-learning process. Specifically, it aimed to:

1. Describe the level of creativity of students exposed to instructional comic strips approach and those exposed to non-instructional comic strips approach in terms of:

- a. Fluency;
- b. Flexibility;
- c. Originality;
- d. Elaboration; and
- e. Connection.

2. Assess the difference between the level of creativity of students when exposed to instructional comic strips approach and those exposed to non-instructional comic strips approach with pretest as covariate.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a quasi-experimental design to examine the effectiveness of integrating the 7E Learning Model with comic strips on the creativity of Grade 8 students at Tongantongan National High School. Two intact sections participated: the Instructional Comic Strip Approach group with 42 students and a control group with 47 students. The intervention was conducted during the fourth quarter of the 2024–2025 academic year, focusing on the science topics: Digestive System: Its Parts and Function, Cell Division: Mitosis and Meiosis, Meiosis, and Phenotypic Expressions of Traits. The treatment group are taught by these topics using the 7E Learning Model supplemented with comic strips, while the Non-Instructional Comic Strip approach received conventional instruction. Creativity was assessed based on fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration, and connection adapted from the SCORE model of Lehmkuhl et al. (2021).

Locale of the Study

Tongantongan National High School, where the study is conducted, is located at P-8, Tongantongan, Valencia City, Bukidnon. During the Academic Year 2024-2025, the school has 30 classrooms with classes spread across eight buildings. There are 44 permanent teachers. In the current year, the school is one of the most competitive and progressing schools in the division of Valencia City, Bukidnon. The School is the second most populated public high school next to Valencia National High School, with a population of approximately 1700 this school year 2024-2025, both in Junior High School and Senior High School.

Participants of the Study

The study participants are two (2) intact classes in the Grade 8 level of Tongantongan National High School under the Basic Education Curriculum officially enrolled in the school year 2024-2025. It is assured that the classes involved in the study are of the same characteristics in terms of academic standing, interest, and limitations.

Research Instrument

The Torrance Test of Creativity (TTCT) rubric assessment of Lehmkuhl et al. (2021) was adapted with modification using the guidelines of Montejo (2023) to determine the level of creativity among students. The adapted TTCT and its scales have five (5) components: fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration and connection. Each component has a rubric for scoring, with a total of 45 points. Science Master Teachers examined the content validity of the modified rubric assessment. For numerical interpretation for scoring on each of the criteria, the researchers used the scoring system of Rababah et al. (2013).

The total mean is used to place students into the following categories:
Numerical Interpretation for Scoring on each of the criteria

<u>Score Range</u>	<u>Qualitative Description</u>
7.3 – 9.0	Very High Level of Creativity (VHLC)
5.5 – 7.2	High Level of Creativity (HLC)
3.7 – 5.4	Moderate Level of Creativity (MLC)
1.9 – 3.6	Low Level of Creativity (LLC)
0 – 1.8	Very Low Level of Creativity (VLLC)

Data Gathering Procedure

A written letter of request is addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent through the Secondary School Principal of Tongantongan National High School, asking permission to conduct the research study during the Grade 8 school year 2024-2025. Also, a letter was sent to the Office of the Institutional Ethics Review Committee (IERC) of Central Mindanao University for the ethical review of the study. A set of questionnaires was administered to 89 (Grade 8) students. Three inter-rater Science Master Teachers assessed the creativity of the students to determine their creativity level in Grade 8 science on both exposed and non-exposed to comic strip approach. The implementation ran through the class for about 4 weeks, and after the 4th week, the students again take the exam. The data that is gathered from this set up shows the creativity of the students in Grade 8 Science.

Statistical Technique

Descriptive statistics such as the mean was used to find out students' creativity in Grade 8 science through an integration of Comic Strips. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to determine any significant difference between the students' creativity of both those exposed to the instructional comic strips approach and those exposed to the non-instructional comic strips approach.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study was conducted at Tongantongan National High School in the Division of Valencia City, Bukidnon, during the academic year 2024–2025. The respondents consisted of two intact sections of Grade 8 students, divided into two groups: 47 students

were exposed to instructional comic strips, while 42 were taught using conventional teaching methods since it utilize a quasi-experimental design. The topics covered in the study included Digestive System: Its Parts and Function, Cell Division: Mitosis and Meiosis, Meiosis: Gametogenesis, and Phenotypic Expressions of Traits.

These lessons were delivered during the fourth quarter of the school year. The study focused on evaluating the potential effects of these visual tools on students' creativity. It was limited to these two sections and used criteria to assess creativity scores.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Secondary Science Students' Level of Creativity

Table 1 presents the mean scores and qualitative descriptions of students' creative thinking skills in both the comic strip and non-comic strip groups, assessed during the pretest and posttest across five indicators: fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration, and connection. In the pretest, both groups reflected similar performance with overall mean scores of 5.84 (HLC) for the comic strip group and 5.77 (HLC) for the non-comic strip group. This indicates that students in both groups initially demonstrated a High Level of Creativity.

Table 1: Secondary Science Students' Level of Creativity in Comic strip approach and Non-Comic strip approach in terms of Pre-Test and Posttest

Creativity	GROUP							
	Comic Strip Approach				Non- Comic Strip Approach			
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest	
	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD	Mean	QD
Elaboration	6.67	HLC	8.03	VHLC	6.58	HLC	6.18	HLC
Flexibility	5.67	HLC	7.42	VHLC	5.67	HLC	5.82	HLC
Originality	6.08	HLC	7.34	VHLC	5.67	HLC	5.82	HLC
Connection	5.58	HLC	7.29	VHLC	5.67	HLC	5.73	HLC
Fluency	5.25	MLC	6.68	HLC	5.25	MLC	5.71	HLC
Overall Mean	5.84	HLC	7.42	VHLC	5.77	HLC	5.84	HLC

Legend:

Score Range	Qualitative Description
7.3 – 9.0	Very High Level of Creativity (VHLC)
5.5 – 7.2	High Level of Creativity (HLC)
3.7 – 5.4	Moderate Level of Creativity (MLC)
1.9 – 3.6	Low Level of Creativity (LLC)
0 – 1.8	Very Low Level of Creativity (VLLC)

However, in the posttest, the comic strip group exhibited remarkable improvement, with their overall mean increasing to 7.42, indicating a Very High Level of Creativity (VHLC). Notably, gains were evident across all five indicators. The 3 indicators who obtain the highest mean score are elaboration, which showed a strong increase from 6.67 (HLC) to 8.03 (VHLC). This means that students exposed in comic strips approach greatly

enhance their ability to give refinements on the topic, enhances ideas through explanations, which will make the learning of the concept more simple and more complete to others. This is being followed by flexibility, with an increase from 5.67 (HLC) to 7.42 (VHLC), showing that students exposed to comic strip approach make them able to shift their perspective and present multiple ideas based on different perspectives. Originality is also among indicators with high mean score, which rose from 6.08 (HLC) to 7.34 (VHLC). This means that the strategy used enabled the learners to be more innovative and create unique ideas. Then connection, which also improved from 5.58 (HLC) to 7.29 (VHLC).

The lowest indicator in the group that was exposed to comic strip approach is fluency, which improved from 5.25 (MLC) to 6.68 (HLC). This means that, though students have been shown to improve their ability to generate scientific ideas with the given problem, it is not as much improvement with other indicators, suggesting that comic strip approach is not that effective in increasing students' fluency. Though different scores are reflected in the table, they show minimal gaps and overall, the results verify a substantial enhancement in all facets of creativity among students taught through comic strip instruction.

In contrast, the non-comic strip group maintained relatively static scores in all indicators between pretest and posttest. Their posttest overall mean was 5.84 (HLC), identical to their pretest, suggesting no significant influence. Each indicator, such as fluency from 5.25 to 5.71, flexibility from 5.67 to 5.82, and originality from 5.67 to 5.82, showed only slight gains, remaining within the same qualitative category of High Level of Creativity.

While most of the indicators show a significant leap between scores among the two groups, the fluency level of both groups has similar qualitative results that fall under HLC from MLC. This means that while both groups perform differently in most areas of creativity, both groups can generate ideas, solutions, or responses from a given situation, and it is not directly affected by some strategy used by the teacher, but by the students themselves. Though this showcases a similar qualitative result in both groups, the majority of the indicators suggest that conventional instruction does not have a great influence on the development of creativity in students.

The results pointed to a huge rise in the creativity of students whose instruction included comic strips, compared to traditional instruction. Posttest scores increased in the comic strip group from an HLC to a VHLC, and the non-comic strip group only increased a little and remained in the same category, HLC. But generally, the difference seen here seems so stark that the integration of visual stories and contextualized illustrations helped the students to be more creative. This shows that comic strip-based instruction is likely to have strong potential as another teaching strategy to improve students' creativity. Aside from that, the comic strip approach caters to multiple learning intelligences, which helps in the improvement of the creativity of learners, as different learning styles are catered in this strategy. Therefore, it is recommended that the teachers in similar settings may consider adopting comic-based strategies to address varied learning styles and improve students' creativity.

This suggests that comic strips as an educational tool help enhance students' creativity. The results of the study reported the same outcome as with other studies. A study regarding brain-based learning textbook embedded with comic strips significantly enhanced students' creative thinking skills. Their study highlighted improvements across creativity components including fluency, flexibility, and elaboration. Students showed high levels of engagement and understanding when materials were visually and contextually rich, similar to those used in this study (Kusumaningrum et al., 2021).

In addition, Sari et al. (2020) conducted a study using comics to teach showed that comics, particularly when tied to familiar cultural themes such as traditional games, helped students improve creativity through visualization and conceptual engagement. These comics encouraged students to form connections, apply ideas in new contexts, and this finding aligned with the improvements seen in the current study.

Furthermore, Casiano and Palacio (2023) also emphasized the value of comic strips in enhancing higher-order thinking skills such as evaluating and predicting, which are closely tied to creativity. Their study revealed a significant difference between pretest and posttest scores of students taught using comic strips, indicating improvement in processing multimodal content. These skills overlap with flexibility and elaboration; the areas where students in the current study also improved.

Rahman and Anas (2024) also concluded that comic-based materials led to a marked increase in creative and critical thinking skills among elementary students learning science. Their research emphasized that comics create a highly motivating learning environment and are effective tools for developing imagination and association, key in building fluency and connection in creative output.

Despite the positive findings, some studies have reported limited or mixed results. For example, a pilot study on the use of digital comics among students found that, while students viewed comics positively, they did not report better understanding or use the comics for studying (Gittens et al., 2023). Also, some research has found no significant difference in learning outcomes when using comics. While some students benefited from graphic novels such as comic strips, others preferred text-only materials due to limited visual literacy skills (Nadia, 2017).

Though negative results are found in some studies, the fact that there was an great increase in students' creativity levels when they had involved in comic strips supports the role of such tools in shaping the creative competencies. It affirms the need for the incorporation of more creative, student-centered classroom instruction, particularly those which give the student the opportunity to reason through the use of artistic and narrative formats in considering science issues. This study shows that comic strips provide structure and freedom: the structure of a storyline and characters, and freedom of imagination to improve and add on concepts to enrich the learning experience of the students.

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Creativity Results between Interventions

Table 2 presents the ANCOVA results comparing the creativity levels of students taught using comic strip instruction versus traditional methods across five indicators: fluency, flexibility, originality, elaboration, and connection. In terms of fluency, students in the comic strip group had a higher mean score of 6.78 (SD = 0.21713) compared to 5.70 (SD = 0.21965) in the non-comic strip group.

Table 2: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Creativity after intervention between classes exposed to Comic strips approach and Non-Comic strip approach.

Indicator	Group	Mean	SD	F-value	Sig	Partial Eta Squared
Fluency	Comic Approach Strip	6.78	.21713	13.16	.000	.134
	Non- Comic Approach Strip	5.70	.21965			
Flexibility	Comic Approach Strip	6.60	.10202	243.02	.000	.741
	Non- Comic Approach Strip	5.64	.70571			
Originality	Comic Approach Strip	7.34	.14843	358.37	.000	.808
	Non- Comic Approach Strip	5.81	.21276			
Elaboration	Comic Approach Strip	8.03	.16392	8.89	.004	.095
	Non- Comic Approach Strip	6.15	.33363			
Connection	Comic Approach Strip	7.29	.21995	2.78	.099	.032
	Non- Comic Approach Strip	5.72	.29388			
CREATIVITY	Comic Approach Strip	7.42	.14625	3003.51	0.000**	.972
	Non- Comic Approach Strip	5.84	.21932			

Legend: ** - significant at 0.05 level

The difference was statistically significant ($F = 13.16$, $p = 0.000$) with a moderate effect size ($PES = 0.134$). For flexibility, the comic strip group also outperformed the non-comic group with a mean of 6.60 (SD = 0.10202) versus 5.64 (SD = 0.70571), showing a highly significant result ($F = 243.02$, $p = 0.000$) and a large effect size ($PES = 0.741$).

Similar patterns were observed in originality and elaboration. The comic strip group had a mean score of 7.34 (SD = 0.14843) in originality, which was significantly higher than the non-comic group's 5.81 (SD = 0.21276). This yielded the highest F-value among the indicators ($F = 358.37$, $p = 0.000$) with a very large effect size (PES = 0.808). For elaboration, students exposed to comic strips scored a mean of 8.03 (SD = 0.16392), while the non-comic group scored 6.15 (SD = 0.33363), resulting in a significant difference ($F = 8.89$, $p = 0.004$, PES = 0.095). The only indicator that did not show a statistically significant difference was connection, where the comic strip group had a higher mean (7.29) than the non-comic group (5.72), but the p-value was above the significance threshold ($F = 2.78$, $p = 0.099$, PES = 0.032). Overall, the total creativity score was significantly higher in the comic strip group ($M = 7.42$, $SD = 0.14625$) than in the non-comic group ($M = 5.84$, $SD = 0.21932$), with a very large effect size ($F = 3003.51$, $p = 0.000$, PES = 0.972), which is considered a very large effect size, meaning that 97.2% of the variance in posttest creativity scores can be attributed to the type of instructional approach used.

These results rejected the null hypothesis and support the conclusion that comic strip-based instruction significantly enhances students' creative thinking across most core dimensions. The strategy encourages students to process and communicate scientific ideas through imaginative storytelling, problem-solving, and visual design whose skills aligned with fluency, flexibility, and originality. The significant differences in these indicators suggest that the comic approach allows for more dynamic and expressive learning compared to conventional strategies.

Although Connection indicator shows no statistical difference between both groups, the slight gain still reflects a tendency for students in the comic strip group to form meaningful associations between ideas. This might be because comic strips have less reflective task which may enhance their creative thinking in connective ideas with real life scenarios. With this, the continued or enhanced integration of this strategy will give clearer results in all aspects of creativity that even the connection aspect of creativity may be strengthened. This indicates that the comic strip method stands out as a highly effective tool in developing creativity in science classrooms.

These results match well with previous studies that have proven that comic strips are effective at increasing creativity. Kusumaningrum et al. (2021) found that students' creative thinking skill as measured by fluency, flexibility, originality and elaboration improved significantly when textbooks with comic strips in brain-based learning approach used in the classrooms. Their findings have a close alignment with the present study and also with how they used visual storytelling and imaginative illustration to give student creative space to work on academic core content lessons.

Similarly, Sari et al. (2020) found that students were statistically more successful in creative problem-solving in the classroom, and that their increased interest in the subject matter was statistically significant in the use of physics comic strips. The comics of the traditional games were used to encourage students to link conceptual knowledge with real contexts which resulted in more superior outputs. In these studies we show content through the comic strip format. Not only it presents content but also use the comic

strip format to inspire creative thinking through envisionment, contextualization and narrative structure.

Also, in the study of Calejesan and Buniel (2021), the use of comic strips was an effective means of teaching in helping students develop scientific thinking and creativity. The current study's results on creativity gains are supported also by the additional element, the visual storytelling elements, in knowledge retention and through imaginative interpretation of scientific concepts. Similar result were obtained by Badeo and Koc (2021) through a comic-based learning module for physics which not only increased STEM students' understanding but also developed students' creative thinking and motivation. And their study clearly demonstrated the increase in students' ability to visualize abstract ideas and express reflected ones in novel ways, thanks to well-designed comics.

Furthermore, this study showed very high mean score as well as statistically significant results as well as surprisingly large effect size meant that use of the comic strip based instruction had a relatively strong positive impact in fostering student creativity in this setting. The combination of this visual and narrative parts offered a stage for the students to express their thoughts, to create relationships and to explore the ideas in the senses. While effectiveness may vary across different learner profiles and school environments, the results of this study suggest that, particularly in rural areas or resource-limited contexts, comic strips can be a valuable tool in promoting creative thinking in science education.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Comic strip instruction enhances students' creativity. Learners who engaged with comic-based activities developed stronger imaginative thinking, demonstrated through higher scores across all five creativity indicators. The use of comics allowed students to express ideas more fluently, flexibly, originally, and with greater elaboration, leading to richer and more diverse outputs compared to the conventional group.

Furthermore, as observed in most creativity indicators, the influence of comic strip instruction on students' creative thinking is strong. While students become more imaginative and expressive, their ability to relate ideas may require further reinforcement. Overall, the comic strip approach proves to be an effective tool for developing creative competencies among junior high school science learners.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are given:

Students are encouraged to take part in activities using comic strips to enrich their creativity. When students draw and think through how ideas are related, it benefits their creativity in scientific matter.

Science teachers are encouraged to integrate comic strip-based instruction in their lessons, especially in science, to improve students' creativity. These tools can make complex topics more engaging and easier to understand.

To support creativity development, Instructional Material makers may design activities that allow students to create or interpret comic strips as part of their performance tasks. These can promote fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration as key components of creativity that this study found significantly improved through visual storytelling.

School administrators and curriculum planners are encouraged to provide support in terms of training, instructional time, and resources for the integration of comic-based strategies into the curriculum. Incorporating such creative and student-centered methods can improve creativity outcomes and promote innovation in science instruction.

Considering the limited gains observed in the creativity indicator "connection," teachers may include explicit activities that focus on linking and synthesizing ideas, such as reflective prompts, concept-mapping within comics, or structured peer discussions. This could further strengthen students' ability to relate scientific ideas meaningfully.

Finally, it is recommended that future researchers explore additional factors that may influence the effectiveness of comic strip-based instruction, such as student learning styles, learners' geographic location, technology orientation, digital comic formats, or longer-term interventions. Further studies can also examine its impact in other subject areas or educational levels to expand the generalizability of the findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher strictly adhered to ethical standards throughout the conduct of the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and since the respondents were minors, parental consent was likewise secured to ensure proper authorization and participation. The respondents were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained at all stages of data collection and analysis, with all personal information kept secure and private. The principles of the Data Privacy Act were strictly followed, and the participants' well-being and safety were prioritized at all times. No conflict of interest was present during the execution of the research, and all forms of plagiarism were consciously avoided by properly citing all sources used. The interpretation of findings was conducted with utmost objectivity and impartiality. The results were used solely for academic and research purposes.

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